

INFLUENCE OF WRITING AND SPEAKING SKILLS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract

When we start to teach foreign language as communication, as a rule, its oral form is distinguished for speaking. The need for a communicative orientation in teaching foreign languages is enshrined in the State Standard and is confirmed by constantly developing intercultural connections, as well as experience in teaching foreign languages. Despite the fact that a lot has been said and written about the role of written speech lately, writing as a productive type of foreign language speech activity still occupies a rather modest place in the foreign language classroom. Analyzing the mechanisms of functioning of types of speech activity, psychologists and methodologists conclude that there are similarities and differences between writing and speaking.

Key words: oral, writing, mechanism, dictation, communicative skills, lexical, grammatical, reading, speaking.

Introduction. In written and oral utterances, the same transitions between externally expressed and internally pronounced linguistic forms function. In the process of writing, a transition occurs from a word spoken aloud or silently to a visible word. When speaking - from a word spoken silently to a word spoken aloud. A written statement is a monologue constructed quite fully. In the absence of direct communication, the writer expands the statement to avoid misunderstanding of his thoughts. In this regard, the letter contains additional information, definitions, and specific features. We strive to present information consistently and logically, clearly and concisely, because... there will be no opportunity to change anything, repeat or clarify what was written. Therefore, it is the written language that is carefully thought out, honed, the author redoes something, reformulates, tries to correctly format what is written. Written text is more clearly structured, because there is an opportunity to check it. The speaker may interrupt and improvise along the way, sometimes losing the logic of the statement. It takes longer to compose a letter. Writing and written speech in the methodology of teaching a foreign language act not only as a means of teaching, but increasingly as the goal of teaching a foreign language. Writing is the technical component of written language. Written speech, along with speaking, is a so-called productive (expressive) type of speech activity and is expressed in fixing certain content with graphic signs.

The psychophysical basis of written speech is the interaction of the motor, visual and auditory-speech motor analyzers. Relying on all analyzers in training gives a much greater effect. According to psychologists, material heard is absorbed by 10%, material seen by 20%, heard and seen by 30%, written down by 50%, when spoken by 70%, when teaching another by 90%. Psychologists believe that the basis of written speech is oral speech. Both speaking

and writing can be traced from the idea (what to say) to the selection of the necessary means (what words are needed, how to combine them in a statement) and to the implementation of the idea by means of language, orally or in writing. If you correctly determine the goals of teaching writing and writing, take into account the role of writing in the development of other skills, use exercises that fully correspond to the goal, and perform these exercises at the appropriate stage of training, then oral speech gradually becomes richer and more logical.

Writing plays an auxiliary role in the development of grammatical skills, when performing written tasks from simple copying to tasks requiring a creative approach, which creates the necessary conditions for memorization. Without support from writing, it is difficult for students to retain lexical and grammatical material in memory. The entire system of language and conditional speech exercises performed in writing refers to educational writing. Written statements, essays, creative dictations, drawing up plans and theses for a message on a given topic, writing a personal or business letter, that is, written stories on given situations, belong to communicative writing. In other words, this is a written speech exercise on a studied or related topic of speaking practice. Written speech is considered as a creative communication skill, understood as the ability to express one's thoughts in writing. To do this, you need to have spelling and calligraphic skills, the ability to compositionally construct and arrange in writing a speech work composed in inner speech, as well as the ability to select adequate lexical and grammatical units.

Training in writing a written message; written and speech exercises for working with printed text; written and speech exercises based on the process of reading, listening and oral communication. Written and speech exercises for working with printed text, in addition to the exercises known to everyone, may contain, according to E. A. Maslyko, the following: - rewrite the text, excluding minor words and sentences from it; - compose a written message to a potential, real or imaginary addressee, using the contents of the letter; - prepare an outline of an oral presentation using a selection of texts on the topic or problem. When reading (viewing, introductory, studying), in the opinion of E. A. Maslyko, written exercises such as: - find in the text and write down the necessary information; - make a written review of a topic or problem, using various sources in a foreign language; - compose annotations on articles in a special journal (collection); - By analogy with the article (its structure), prepare material for the proposed publication in a special journal; - while reading literature (texts), make written notes for subsequent work with the material.

The ability to express your thoughts in writing in a foreign language should be developed consistently and constantly. To solve this problem, there are a number of exercises of a reproductive and productive nature. Exercises offered, for example, by the German methodologist Gerhard Neuner, are compiled in a certain sequence from simple to complex, from reproduction to forming one's own opinion and position. All exercises are performed in writing. In our opinion, the following tasks are of interest: - restore the beginning and end of the story; - restore the dialogue based on individual "guiding" remarks; - change the type of text (message to conversation, dialogue to description); - describe an ambiguous situation in various texts and dialogues; - explain the contradiction between textual and illustrative information; - respond to the letter by letter, telephone conversation, conversation, etc.; - select keywords that lead to a certain pre-known result, etc. Writing a letter is a very

successful form of exercise that is multifunctional in nature. To learn to write a letter, you need to start with a series of speech exercises.

If we consider writing in general as a productive communicative activity, the need for which manifests itself in life through personal motives (write a letter, a statement) or social necessity (a report, a report), then in the process of teaching foreign languages, written communicative exercises with corresponding tasks seem logical. As for the formation of the above-mentioned needs, in the process of teaching a foreign language it is, as a rule, replaced by the teacher setting an educational and methodological task. The problem statement contains a goal that the student implements in writing. As is known, in modern methods of teaching foreign languages, there are different approaches to teaching writing.

Thus, E. N. Solovova distinguishes directive, linguistic and activity approaches. Since the goal of the directive (formal) linguistic approach is, first of all, the correctness of what is written, and the content side fades into the background and the main features of the linguistic or formal-structural approach are "rigid" control of the process of written speech, a large number of receptive-reproductive exercises, then this The article is aimed at an activity-based or content-semantic approach to teaching writing. In this approach, writing is viewed as a creative process during which awareness and formation of thoughts occur.

Experimenting with linguistic forms, discovering something new in a language, feeling its harmony and rhythm, enjoying the beauty of its sound, humor - all this should not only be allowed and recognized. The teacher must facilitate this if he wants to get students to express themselves creatively in writing. If there is fear in a lesson, then the atmosphere is absolutely unpromising for creativity, including creative writing. The most important goal of instructional creative writing is to generate and maintain joy in the writing process. Productive creative writing can be used early in learning. First, we can recommend various types of supports: visual clarity (household items, pictures, photographs), audio clarity (audio texts, songs, instrumental pieces of music), written clarity (poems, stories, quotes, proverbs, etc.).

As students gain experience in creative writing, the role of supports decreases and tasks without support are possible, for example, spontaneous creative writing about what worries you most at the moment, amuses you, surprises you, outrages you, etc. Interesting exercises based on the so-called musical text, i.e. instrumental music without words. The listener's subjective associations seem to be influenced by the mood of the musical work. These associations are the focus. Music itself loses its independent sound. In this case, it interests us as a means of stimulating creativity and creative writing. Either its relaxing or affective influence depends on the choice of a piece of music. For example, meditative music works well when describing fantastic travels. Creative written stories from the perspective of a hero or any subject about the history of his life, a written continuation of an interrupted story or a famous literary work, a mini-essay or an essay based on a selected quote. Written creative tasks have enormous learning potential and, in our opinion, can be used in every foreign language lesson. The teacher selects and includes them in the curriculum based on educational goals and the level of students' skills.

Conclusion. In recent years, the role of writing in teaching a foreign language has gradually increased, and, in a sense, writing is beginning to be considered as a reserve in increasing the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language. It is impossible not to take into account the practical significance of written speech communication in the light of modern means of

communication, such as e-mail, the Internet, etc. In the latter case, writing as a type of verbal communication develops on the basis of only authentic material. Foreign internships for students, graduate students and young scientists require the ability to take notes in a foreign language, compose and fill out a questionnaire, answer questionnaire questions, write an application for admission to study or work, write a short or detailed autobiography, write personal or business letters using the required form speech etiquette of native speakers, including a form of business etiquette.

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